

Impact of superchilling storage temperatures on beef quality: Micro-CT analysis of ice recrystallization kinetics in partially frozen samples

Anjelina W Mwakosya^{*} , Graciela Alvarez, Fatou Toutie Ndoye

Université Paris–Saclay, INRAE, FRISE, 92761, Antony, France

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the microstructure changes of partially frozen beef under different superchilling storage conditions and relate these changes to quality degradation. Beef samples were partially frozen in an air blast freezer with a heat transfer coefficient of $112 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and an air temperature of $-32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 min following storage at $-1.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $-2.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $-4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $-5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 21 days. "X-ray micro-computed tomography (μCT), a non-destructive 3D imaging technique was used to visualize and quantify ice crystal characteristic, including ice volume fractions, ice crystal size, number and distribution". Recrystallization kinetics were modelled using the asymptotic Ostwald ripening equation and correlated with quality degradation rate through Pearson correlation analysis. Immediately after partial freezing, the average initial ice volume fraction, mean equivalent diameter, and crystal number were $31 \pm 1 \%$, $36.0 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, and $421,182 \pm 16,524$, respectively. Over storage time, ice volume fraction and crystal size increased significantly ($p < 0.05$), while crystal number decreased, leading to increased drip loss, and reduced firmness of beef upon thawing. In addition, recrystallization rates increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) with decreasing storage temperature specifically within a range of $-1.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $-5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as lower temperatures resulted in higher ice fractions and more heterogeneous crystal size distributions, thereby promoting recrystallization. A high regression coefficient ($R^2 > 0.9$) indicated a strong fit of the recrystallization rate's temperature dependence to the Arrhenius model. Recrystallization rate was strongly correlated with all quality degradation rates ($R^2 > 0.9$). Overall, this study demonstrates the critical role of recrystallization in driving deterioration of partially frozen beef and highlights the value of X-ray μCT for non-invasive monitoring microstructure changes during superchilled storage.

1. Introduction

Superchilling is a promising food preservation technology that involves partial crystallization of water in the muscle tissue of the food product. This process involves a thermodynamic physical phenomenon where some water is converted to ice based on the degree of superchilling. In this context, the degree of superchilling or ice volume fraction must be precisely controlled within the range of 30–35 %, as it is a key factor in determining the final quality of superchilled food (Bahuaud et al., 2008; Stevik and Clausen, 2011). Moreover, properties of the formed ice crystals, such as size, distribution and location also play a crucial role in determining the final quality and stability of food (Kaale and Eikevik, 2015; El-Abdi et al., 2025). These microstructural properties are highly influenced by storage temperature, time, and temperature fluctuations, which are very common in cold chains. The main causes of these fluctuations are uneven cooling within the storage unit, repeated

door openings and ambient temperature changes, long transportation time, power outage, faulty equipment, which happens during subsequent storage. Minor temperature deviations can lead to recrystallization that influences crystal growth and subsequent quality deterioration or even complete loss of food products, especially with superchilled food as they are stored close to their initial freezing point (Kaale et al., 2013; Lu et al., 2019). The driving force mechanism behind recrystallization is the difference in energy between small and large ice crystals (Mazur, 1984; Hagiwara et al., 2006). Smaller ice crystals are less stable due to their high surface area to volume ratios; thus, to equilibrate thermodynamically, they tend to minimize their surface-free energy (Pronk et al., 2005; Cook and Hartel, 2010). Several mechanisms of recrystallization have been widely described in the literature, including: isomass, accretive, and migratory recrystallization (Bevilacqua and Zaritzky, 1982; Dang et al., 2021). Among these, migratory recrystallization, which is also known as Ostwald ripening, has been mostly suggested by several studies to describe recrystallization in frozen food products

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: anjelina-william.mwakosya@inrae.fr (A.W. Mwakosya).

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Nomenclature

k	Recrystallization rate ($\mu\text{m}/\text{day}^{1/n}$)
\bar{d}	Mean crystal size
\bar{d}_0	Initial mean crystal size
t	Time (day)
E_a	Activation energy ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)
K_0	Pre-exponential constant factor,
R	Universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)
T	Storage temperature of the product (K)
t_{pf}	Partial freezing time (seconds)
t_f	Initial freezing point in $^{\circ}\text{C}$
t_a	Air temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$
ρ	Density of beef (kg/m^3)
L_0	Latent heat of fusion of water ($333.6 \text{ kJ}/\text{kg}$)
P	Shape factor (16 for infinite cylinder)
Q	Shape factor (4 for infinite cylinder)
h_a	Heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)
K	Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$)
TBARS	Thiobarbituric acid-reactive substances content
TVB-N	Total volatile nitrogen basic compounds
PCM	Phase change material

(Hartel, 1998; Roos, 2021). Ostwald ripening becomes more rapid during temperature fluctuations, as repeated ice melting–diffusion–refreezing causes small ice crystals to melt when the temperature rises, causing water to diffuse into the bulk matrix and deposit on the surface of large ice crystals during cooling (Ndoye and Alvarez, 2015; van Westen and Groot, 2018). This process results in the growth of large ice crystals and consequently a reduction of the overall number of ice crystals (Syamaladevi et al., 2012). Formation of large ice crystals leads to microstructure changes that directly influence the quality of superchilled food, such as alteration in texture, higher drip loss, and loss of nutritional and sensory values (Kaale et al., 2011). Few studies have evaluated the effect of superchilling storage conditions on microstructure changes of superchilled food. For instance, Kaale et al. (2013) and Kaale and Eikevik (2015) demonstrated a significant difference between ice crystal size immediately after superchilling and after superchilled storage of salmon fillets. Moreover, a significant growth of ice crystal size was noted after 14–21 days of storage at -1.7°C . Very few studies have combined the effects of superchilling storage conditions on the quality and microstructure of superchilled food products (Kaale and Eikevik, 2014; Xu et al., 2020; Tao et al., 2023; El-Abdi et al., 2025). However, most of these studies used 2D microscopic analysis techniques to monitor the change of ice crystals. Still, these techniques are limited because they are cumbersome and require tedious sample preparation (invasive). This, in turn, makes it difficult to follow the same sample along the storage duration. Moreover, 2D information only depends on the visualized section plane, thus to analyse the whole image clearly and quantitatively becomes a challenge (Dalen and Koster, 2012). Therefore, there is a need for a reliable method that is non-invasive and non-destructive to the sample, for visualization and quantification of a 3D image. X-ray micro-computed tomography (μCT) is an imaging technique that produces a number of X-ray radiographs shadows of the sample, which are then reconstructed to get a 3D image. X-ray μCT coupled with a cooling stage allows the same frozen sample to be monitored over the whole storage duration, as shown in several previous studies (Vicent et al., 2018; Zennoune et al., 2022). X-ray μCT has been applied to study microstructure evolution for frozen food (Vicent et al., 2018; Mulot et al., 2019; Vicent, 2019; Zennoune et al., 2021; Latil et al., 2022, 2022) and more recently to superchilled chicken breast meat (El-Abdi et al., 2025). The authors attempted to establish a link between

ice volume fraction and quality parameters but concluded that, to gain deeper insight into the mechanisms occurring during the superchilling process and their impact on quality, it is essential to also quantify ice crystal size, number and distribution rather than relying solely on ice volume fraction. Moreover, extrapolating findings obtained in other species, namely, fish, pork and poultry products, to beef is not straightforward because there are relevant compositional and structural differences among species. Salmon muscle, for instance, is higher in lipid content and has less connective tissue, making it more prone to lipid oxidation but less resistant to structural collapse (Chan et al., 2022). Chicken breast, however, has lower myoglobin content and a simpler muscle fiber organization compared to beef (Kim et al., 2020). On the other hand, pork muscle is characterized by an intermediate composition, with relatively high-water content and moderate connective tissue, which may explain its sensitivity to water migration and drip loss under superchilled storage. In contrast, beef is distinguished by higher myoglobin content, denser connective tissue, and a different water distribution between intra- and extracellular spaces (Juárez et al., 2011). These specific features directly affect ice crystal formation and growth, and consequently the pathways of quality degradation (e.g., drip loss, textural softening, lipid and protein oxidation). More recently, the effect of superchilling conditions on various quality attributes of beef meat has been investigated by the research team involved in the present study (Mwakosya et al., 2025).

To the best of our knowledge, no work has explored the use of X-ray μCT to study microstructure characteristics for partially frozen beef on qualitative and quantitative 3D image analysis within a range of superchilling and mild-freezing temperatures (-1.8°C to -5°C). It is highly critical to understand the microstructure evolution during partial freezing and subsequent storage in order to define the optimum conditions that minimize recrystallization and preserve beef quality. In addition, no study has developed recrystallization kinetics of partially frozen beef and relate them to quality degradation during storage. Understanding the mechanisms of recrystallization can be useful in optimizing the superchilling process in general.

Therefore, the objectives of this work were: (i) to study the effects of superchilling storage conditions on the microstructure of partially frozen beef, (ii) to relate microstructure evolution with quality parameters (texture, drip loss, color, pH, Thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS), and total volatile basic nitrogen (TVB-N)) and (iii) to develop recrystallization kinetics based on Ostwald ripening model and correlate it with quality degradation rates. Lean beef was chosen as a case study, because of its distinct muscle composition and industrial relevance, providing new insights into the broader applicability of superchilling preservation across different animal species.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

Fresh lean beef tenderloin samples (psoas major muscle) were obtained from a local butchery (Antony, France), approximately 24 h postmortem. The samples were sourced from a 24-month-old *Bos taurus* cattle. Upon reaching the laboratory, the samples were immediately placed in the refrigerator at 2°C for 1 hour for temperature equilibration before partial freezing. For microstructure analysis, the samples were carefully cut from the inner part of the beef matrix in small cylindrical shapes with dimensions of 6 mm in diameter and 2 cm in height. They were inserted in plastic straws (with the exact dimensions) for easy handling during X-ray μCT image acquisition. The experiments were conducted with four replicates across two different batches to ensure reproducibility of results.

2.2. Superchilling process – experimental design

The superchilling process was performed in two steps as described by

Mwakosya et al. (2025); The first and second steps were partial freezing and subsequent superchilled storage, respectively. Initially the samples were subjected to partial freezing in an air blast freezer (Bonnet Biostore Turbo M, Bonnet Neve, EPTA, France). The samples were placed on an open tray inside the freezing cabinet operating at a heat transfer coefficient of 112 W/m²K and air temperature of -32 °C for a duration of 2 min. The partial freezing time was calculated using Plank’s equation, Eq. (1) based on an assumed ice volume fraction of 30 % (Mwakosya et al., 2025). The values of the parameters P and Q were set to 16 and 4 respectively, based on the Planck model for an infinite cylindrical shape.

$$t_{pf} = \frac{\rho L_0}{T_f - T_a} \left(\frac{d}{Qh_a} + \frac{d^2}{Pk} \right) \quad (1)$$

After partial freezing, the samples were immediately and equally put in four different polypropylenes plastic containers each closed with snap-on plastic lids (Amazon.fr, France) and they were placed in a 5 cm-thick expanded polystyrene box in order to achieve constant temperature during storage. These boxes were placed in four distinct chest freezers (Electrolux ECM30132W, Stockholm, Sweden), each of which was set at a constant temperature: (i) -5 °C, (ii) -4 °C, (iii) -2.8 °C, (iv) -1.8 °C. The storage temperatures were potentially selected based on the initial freezing point of the beef -0.89 °C which was experimentally determined by extrapolating the plateau of the freezing curve, following the method described by (Pham, 1984). The temperatures; -1.8 °C and -2.8 °C, were purposefully chosen as they represent the superchilled range typically 1– 2 °C points below the initial freezing point of beef (El-Abdi et al., 2025). On the other hand, other storage temperatures; -5 °C and -4 °C, simulated cases where the temperature could drop significantly below the desired superchilled range and cause subsequent effects on the microstructure, hence quality of beef meat. The samples were analysed for microstructure before (fresh) and immediately after partial freezing and during storage, where sampling was done after every 7 days, as day 1, day 7, day 14, and day 21.

2.4. Characterisation of the microstructure of beef using X-ray μCT

2.4.1. Image acquisition

A high-resolution X-ray μCT (DeskTom RX 130, RX Solution, Chavanod, France) was used to acquire scans of partially frozen beef

Fig. 1. Parts of the cooling stage. (a) circular cap of the insulating double jacket cylindrical box (b) insulating double jacket cylindrical box filled with polyurethane (c) double jacket cylindrical box containing PCM at -20 °C (d) cap of the double jacket cylindrical box filled with PCM (e) plastic straw containing partially frozen beef.

samples. To prevent the sample from melting during the entire scanning time, the samples were first placed in a cylindrical box (Fig. 1) that incorporated a frozen gelled phase change material (PCM) at -20 °C, following a similar method to that described by Mulo et al. (2019) and Vicent (2019). A cylinder is the most suitable geometry for scanning in order to reduce artefacts, thus using a plastic straw was a good choice. Moreover, the scanning accuracy depends on the distance between the sample and the X-ray source, which is constrained by sample size. Therefore, a small sample close to the source provided higher scanning accuracy. The X-ray tube was set at 53 kV and 150 μA, with a voxel resolution of 8.88 μm. A total number of 889 projection images was recorded over a 180° rotation with a 0.2° step, making a total scanning time of 14 min per sample to capture 1337 images. After scanning, the sample were immediately put back to the storage freezers.

2.4.2. Image reconstruction

The software, Xact 2® (RX Solution, Chavanod, France) was used to convert the raw acquisition data (2D radiographs) to 2D cross-section images that are stacked together to form a highly detailed 3D representation of the internal structure of the sample. This process is done by applying the most common arithmetic algorithm called Filtered back-projection (Islam, 2021), which combines all the voxel intensities of the scanned sample (Ramachandran and Lakshminarayanan, 1971; Kim et al., 2022). There are two steps involved: 1) filtering, where each 2D image is filtered to enhance high-frequency fine details (phase-contrast correction) and reduce the artefacts. 2) back-projection; after filtering, the 2D images are then back-projected to reconstruct the original image into 3D space (Vlassenbroeck et al., 2007). The reconstructed 3D image consisted of 1337 slices encoded in 8-bit precision, which corresponded to the intensity range of 255 levels (0–254). This encoding makes subsequent image processing easier since it reduces computational load while maintaining sufficient detail for analysis. Additionally, the reconstructed 3D image shows distinct grey levels which enable a clear differentiation of three phases (air, ice, and unfrozen regions) in the sample. For instance, as illustrated in the slice in Fig. 2, the black regions correspond to air space created when beef was placed in the plastic straws; the light grey areas represent the unfrozen phase, whilst the dark grey regions indicate the presence of ice crystals. The most important parameters to consider during reconstruction are noise filtering such as ring artifact correction, smoothing, offset correlation and phase contrast correction (Russ, 2015; Graas et al., 2024).

2.4.3. Image processing and analysis

The image process workflow for analyzing the microstructure of beef involved two main steps:

1) Image segmentation to obtain ice volume fractions (%)

Segmentation is a crucial step because most of the post-processing image analysis requires segmented images. Therefore, at this step, the

Fig. 2. Grey level of X-ray μCT reconstructed image.

ice phase was segmented with the rest of the components (air and unfrozen phase) from the whole volume of a reconstructed image (as shown in Fig. 3) using AVIZO software (Thermo Fischer Scientific, NYSE, USA). The segmentation process was performed using grey level thresholding following the method based on attenuation coefficient of references, previously reported by Vicent et al. (2017). In this study, frozen pure water was used as a reference to determine the X-ray attenuation coefficients of ice. For this purpose, pure water was frozen at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a straw and scanned under the same conditions as the partially frozen beef samples. The grey-level range obtained for the ice phase was 81–194, while values between 195 and 254 were assigned to the unfrozen phase. Accordingly, the following threshold values were defined: air (0–80), ice (81–194), and unfrozen phase (195–254). These optimized threshold grey level values were applied to each of the scanned sample to segment the ice phase. After segmentation, the ice volume fraction was calculated by the ratio of volume of ice to the total volume of ice and unfrozen phase.

2) Ice crystal size and number analysis

After segmentation, the following step is to analyse individual ice crystals for size and number. To achieve this, the segmented image was first cropped to get a representative elementary volume (REV) of $4.26 \times 10^{-7}\text{ m}^3$ using the method previously described by Vicent et al. (2017). Then, a threshold value of ice (81–194) was applied to a selected REV to segment only the ice phase from the rest of the components. Afterwards, the segmented REV image was then despeckled to remove unwanted artefacts and improve the quality of the image. On the other hand, h-extrema watershed was applied to the cropped raw reconstructed image (REV) to separate the touching or overlapping ice crystals. An arithmetic operation was then applied where the thresholded image (A) and watershed-segmented image (B) was subtracted (A–B) to get only the ice phase with individual ice crystals. The resulting image was then labelled, followed by a border kill operation, which was performed to remove ice crystals intersecting the image boundaries. The label analysis operation was applied to extract quantitative information, including ice crystal size expressed as equivalent diameter and crystal number. Finally, the results were filtered to include only ice crystals with an equivalent diameter greater than twice the voxel size, which was $18\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ using an analysis filter operation, based on the spatial resolution analysis described by Vicent (2019). The output of the image processing step is the labeled 3D image as shown in Fig. 4. This 3D output served as a basis for computing the microstructure of the beef sample quantitatively, enabling detailed analysis of ice crystal size and distribution and the number of ice crystals.

Fig. 3. The right image is a segmented X-ray μCT horizontal slice of partially frozen beef with three distinct colors showing three different phases: light blue–air; dark blue–ice; red–unfrozen phases.

2.6. Modelling

2.6.1. Kinetic modelling of the ice recrystallization process

The evolution of ice crystal size for partially frozen beef over time was modeled using the Ostwald ripening model, which was initially developed by Lifshitz and Slyozov (1961). The mathematical expression is given by Eq. (2)

$$\bar{d}(t) = \bar{d}_0 + kt^{1/n} \quad (2)$$

where, $\bar{d}(t)$ represents the mean ice crystal size at time t and \bar{d}_0 is the initial mean ice crystal size. The parameter n describes the dominant mass transfer phenomenon that causes ice recrystallization. Generally, when $n = 2$; it corresponds to convection-limited mass transfer, while $n = 3$ indicates a diffusion-limited mass transfer (Prunk et al., 2005). In this study, n was set to 3 to reflect the predominance of Ostwald ripening, following a diffusion-controlled mechanism. Ostwald maturation takes place through molecular diffusion, and due to its inherently slow nature, it is assumed that diffusion is the rate-determining step in both crystal dissolution and growth (Nanev, 2023). The coefficient k represents the recrystallization rate ($\mu\text{m}/\text{day}^{1/3}$), which varies with storage temperature. The temperature dependency k of the recrystallization rate was modelled using the Arrhenius equation Eq. (3).

$$k = k_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where k_0 is the pre-exponential constant factor, E_a is the activation energy (J/mol), R is the universal gas constant ($8.314\text{ J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) and T is the storage temperature of the product recorded after every 5 s for 21 days of storage. k_0 and E_a were obtained from a slope of $\ln k$ vs inverse of storage temperature ($1/T$).

To estimate parameter k , the experimental data (mean ice crystal size under different storage conditions of $-1.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) were fitted to Eq. (2) by minimizing the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as expressed by Eq. (4).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\bar{d}_{exp}(t_i) - \bar{d}_{pre}(t_i))^2 \quad (4)$$

Where $\bar{d}_{exp}(t_i)$ is the experimentally measured ice crystal size (μm), $\bar{d}_{pre}(t_i)$ is the predicted average ice crystal size (μm), and N represents the total number of experimental data points i . The parameter optimization was carried out using a direct method (simplex) in MATLAB *fminsearch* function.

2.6.1. Model validation

The mean ice crystal sizes of partially frozen beef stored at $-1.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ were fitted to obtain the parameter k . Following this, the parameters k_0 and E_a were then obtained from the slope of their $\ln k$ vs ($1/T$). For validating the recrystallization model, these parameters were then used to predict the mean ice crystal sizes at a storage temperature of $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The predicted values were then compared with the experimentally measured average ice crystal sizes, and the model's accuracy was assessed using the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) calculated according to Eq. (5).

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum \left| \frac{C_{obs} - C_{pre}}{C_{obs}} \right| \quad (5)$$

2.7. Statistical analysis

The data were tested for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test and homogeneity of variance via Levene's test. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to analyse the variation among all measured parameters, and Turkey's post hoc test was applied to verify if there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the ice volume fraction, ice

Fig. 4. Image processing workflow using AVIZO software (Thermo Fischer Scientific, NYSE, USA).

crystal size, and number in beef samples. The relationship between recrystallization rate and kinetic quality degradation rate (Mwakosya et al., 2025) was established using Pearson correlation. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software package at a significance level of 95 % (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 19, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). All results are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean. (SME, $n = 3$). All graphs were obtained using GraphPad Prism 8 (Graph Pad Software, Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Qualitative analysis of microstructure

X-ray μ CT 2D horizontal slices of the fresh and partially frozen beef sample (obtained immediately after pre-freezing), and those stored under different temperature conditions are shown in Fig. 5. The fresh sample exhibited a uniform and homogeneous cellular fibre matrix with no visible ice crystals (Fig. 5a). The partially frozen sample (Fig. 5b), however, contained uniformly distributed ice crystals and was used as a baseline for comparison and understanding microstructure changes happening during storage. At day 1 of storage (Fig. 5c), the ice crystals were already distributed homogeneously throughout the whole volume of the sample, implying temperature equalization initiated further ice nucleation toward the center of the sample. Similar observations have been previously reported by Kaale and Eikevik (2015) for a superchilled Atlantic salmon and by El-Abdi et al. (2025) for chicken breast meat right after day 1 of storage.

Over time, a clear ice crystal growth was observed from day 1 to day 21 of storage. Under stable superchilling conditions for instance; -1.8°C and -2.8°C , the ice phase gradually evolved into distinct band-like structures with increasingly defined edges. These indicate both continued nucleation and recrystallization, particularly as ice crystals grow larger. This process changes the spatial distribution and shape of the ice, moving from uniformly dispersed small crystals to larger, elongated, and more structured bands within the tissue. At -4°C and -5°C , the band-like distribution of ice crystals became more pronounced and heterogeneously distributed. At these temperatures, small ice crystals are energetically unstable due to higher surface-to-volume ratio (Tan et al., 2021). As a result, they tend to melt and refreeze on the surface of larger ice crystals and enhance a visible ice crystal growth.

3.2. Quantitative analysis of microstructure

3.2.1. Ice volume fraction

Fig. 6a illustrates the evolution of ice volume fraction changes in beef samples stored under two superchilling conditions (-1.8°C and -2.8°C) and two mild-freezing conditions (-4°C and -5°C) over four storage durations: 1, 7, 14, and 21 days. At each time point, there is a clear and statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), as expected, increase in ice volume fraction is observed as the storage temperature decreases. The lowest temperature (-5°C) consistently results in the highest ice volume fractions, followed by -4°C , -2.8°C , and -1.8°C , highlighting the strong influence of storage temperature on the extent of water freezing in the meat matrix. At -1.8°C , the ice volume fraction remains relatively stable over time, with no significant variation ($p > 0.05$). These observations are in accordance with those reported by El-Abdi et al. (2025) for chicken breast meat stored within the same temperature range. On the other hand, ice volume fractions for samples stored at -2.8°C , remain unchanged for day 1 and day 7, while significant changes were observed at day 14 and day 21. This may be due to progressive ice crystal growth in the whole volume of the product due to prolonged storage. In contrast, for the mild-freezing temperatures (-4°C and -5°C), ice volume fractions increase significantly over the storage period ($p < 0.05$). This trend indicates ongoing physical transformations such as ice crystal growth through further recrystallization or gradual water migration into the frozen phase. Moreover, these lower temperatures create a higher driving force for further nucleation and subsequent ice crystal growth, hence increased ice volume fraction (Arellano et al., 2012). These observations suggest that the storage temperature is a highly influential factor for preserving the quality and structural integrity of the superchilled samples.

3.2.2. Ice crystal size and number

Fig. 6b shows the evolution of ice crystal size during storage of superchilled samples. The average diameter of the partially frozen sample was $36 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$. This value is similar to that reported by (Kaale et al., 2013) for white muscle of Atlantic salmon (salmon salar). However, at day 1 of storage, they obtain a crystal size of 4 times larger than at day 0 for a superchilled storage temperature of $-1.7 \pm 0.3^\circ\text{C}$ which was not the case in our study as a value of $40.0 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ was obtained for the same storage temperature and time. Nevertheless, this might be due to difference in sample composition or experimental conditions. In this study, it was observed that the size of ice crystals for the partially frozen sample was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than those stored under different temperature conditions. During partial freezing, ice forms on

Fig. 5. (a) X-ray μCT 2D horizontal slices of fresh and partially-frozen sample; (b) Images (A1–D4) Partially frozen beef samples stored at different temperature conditions (–1.8 °C, –2.8 °C, –4 °C and –5 °C) for different analysis time point (day 1, day 7, day 14 and day 21).

the surface while the center remains unfrozen, creating a thermal gradient within the sample. Consequently, during storage, temperature equalization occurs between the surface and core, leading to recrystallization, which in turn influences ice crystal growth. In addition, according to Kaale et al. (2014), temperature fluctuations occurring as the sample is moving from the partial freezing temperature of –30 °C to a higher temperature storage, which in our case was (–1.8 °C, –2.8 °C, –4 °C, and –5 °C), should also contribute to recrystallization.

As shown in Fig. 6b, the size of ice crystals for beef samples stored at –1.8 °C and –2.8 °C increased significantly between day 1 and day 7 of

storage but remain unchanged throughout the whole storage duration ($p > 0.05$). These results are consistent with those reported by Tao et al. (2023) for pork and Kaale and Eikevik (2013) for salmon. They both argued that nucleation and ice crystal growth is practically unavoidable and eventually after temperature equalization, no more nucleation and ice crystal growth observed for this superchilled temperature range. Similarly, the ice crystal number reduced significantly between day 1 and day 7 of storage and eventually there was no significant difference for day 14 and day 21 (Fig. 6c; $p > 0.05$). On the other hand, samples stored at –4 °C and –5 °C had significantly increase of ice crystal size (p

Fig. 6. (a) Ice volume fraction; (b) Ice crystal size (Mean equivalent diameter); (c) Ice crystal number for partially frozen beef samples stored at -1.8°C , -2.8°C , -4°C and -5°C for 21 days. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean (SEM) calculated from three replicates ($n = 3$). Note: The data were expressed by the mean \pm standard error of the mean. Different superscript lowercase letters (a–d) in the same storage time indicated the significant difference ($p < 0.05$). Different superscript uppercase letters (A–D) in the same storage temperature group indicated the significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

< 0.05) and significantly reduction of crystal numbers ($p < 0.05$) throughout the whole storage time. This implies the influence of storage temperature on crystal growth and reduction of crystal number. The larger ice crystals may significantly disrupt the microstructure of beef, leading to quality loss such as texture degradation and drip loss. This was demonstrated by Mwakosya et al. (2025), who investigated the impact of similar temperature conditions on various quality attributes of beef meat within the framework of the present study. At the end of storage time, ice crystal size increased by 25 %, 43 %, 49 % and 68 % and ice crystal number reduced by 58 %, 60 %, 61 % and 68 % for -1.8°C , -2.8°C , -4°C , and -5°C , respectively. For this reason, analyzing ice

crystal size evolution during storage is very important to understand the extent of recrystallization and its potential impact on the quality of partially frozen food.

3.3. Ice crystal distribution

3.3.1. Effect of storage temperature and duration

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 both show the quantitative analysis of cumulative probability for ice crystal size distribution according to storage time and storage temperature, respectively. The effect of storage temperature is shown in Fig. 7 (A–D) whereas the results show that, as the temperature

Fig. 7. Cumulative probability distribution of ice crystal equivalent diameter (μm) for superchilled beef samples - effect of storage temperature.

decreases, the probability curve shifts to the right indicating a gradual increase in the size of ice crystals compared to the partially frozen sample (control). These trends suggest that lower temperatures promote the formation of larger ice crystals, likely due to recrystallization. Fig. 8 (A–D) shows the effect of storage duration. It can be seen clearly that, at day 1 of storage, the ice crystals were relatively smaller in size compared to the rest of the storage times. As storage progresses, the curve shifts to the right further from day 7, day 14, to day 21, implying ice crystal growth. These results are consistent with those observed for ice crystal size and crystal number (Fig. 6b and Fig. 6c). To the best of our knowledge, this research appears to be the first to evaluate ice crystal size distribution for partially frozen beef during storage. However, similar works have been done on frozen apple (Vicent et al., 2017) and frozen carrot (Vicent et al., 2018).

3.7. Recrystallization model kinetics

The results for recrystallization rate k and corresponding MSE for the three storage temperatures (-1.8°C , -2.8°C , and -5°C) are shown in Table 1. Within the studied temperature range (-1.8°C to -5°C), recrystallization rates increased significantly ($p < 0.005$) with the decrease in storage temperature. This trend can be explained by the combined effect of ice fraction and ice crystal size distribution at lower

storage temperatures. At -5°C the ice volume fraction was higher than at -1.8°C and -2.8°C (Fig. 6a), leading to reduced free water and a denser packing of ice crystals within the muscle tissue. Under these conditions, crystals are closer to each other, which favors recrystallization through Ostwald ripening, as the proximity of differently sized crystals facilitates the diffusion of water molecules from small to large crystals. In parallel, ice crystal size distributions were more heterogeneous at -5°C , compared with -1.8°C and -2.8°C , as shown in Fig. 7 and 8, further enhancing ice recrystallization.

From a mechanistic perspective, the thermodynamic forces that enhance recrystallization become stronger at -5°C (Bhugra and Pikal, 2008). According to Gibbs–Thomson effect, as mentioned earlier, the smaller ice crystals have higher surface energy and are surrounded by regions of larger solute concentrations large ice crystals. Therefore, based on Fick's first law of diffusion, the molecules migrate from areas surrounding small ice crystals toward those surrounding larger ice crystals (Jackson, 2010). In turn, during Ostwald maturation, the small ice crystals dissolve and their water molecules diffuse and re-deposit onto larger ice crystals, which continue to grow (Nanev, 2023). This phenomenon leads to a decrease in the number of ice crystals and an increase in the size of the remaining ice crystals, in accordance with the observations of the present work.

Fig. 9 shows the fitting of the experimental mean equivalent

Fig. 8. Cumulative probability distribution of ice crystal equivalent diameter (μm) for superchilled beef samples– effect of storage duration.

Table 1

Fitted parameters k of the Ostwald ripening model (with a fixed $n = 3$) and MSE.

Storage temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	k ($\mu\text{m}/\text{day}^{1/3}$)	MSE
-1.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	4.52	1.19
-2.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	6.85	2.19
-5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	11.58	2.99

diameter with those predicted by the Ostwald ripening model. The figure shows good agreement between experimental and predicted data. The difference between experimental measured data and the predicted one was $<5\%$ for most of the data points, and it did not exceed 10% for all data, as shown on the parity plot. The mean difference between the experimental and model predictions was 0.72, 0.78, and 0.10 for storage temperatures of -1.8°C , -2.8°C , and -5°C , respectively. These differences are significantly lower than the average standard mean error of the experimental measurement, which were 1.55, 1.16, and 1.97 for the same storage temperatures. These results suggest that the recrystallization kinetics for partially frozen beef during storage between -1.8°C and -5°C , can be accurately described by the Ostwald ripening model. In literature, this is the first study to develop a recrystallization model for partially frozen food. Although previous works have used the same model for developing recrystallization kinetics, in full frozen food products such as ice cream (Hartel, 1998; Flores and Goff, 1999; Ndoye and Alvarez, 2015), carrots (Adapa et al., 2000; Vicent et al., 2020), and beef (Bevilacqua and Zaritzky, 1982; Martino and Zaritzky, 1988).

Fig. 9. Parity plot of the experimental and predicted ice crystal mean size for partially frozen beef stored at -1.8°C , -2.8°C and -5°C .

Fig. 10. Validation of model prediction. The dotted line represents the experimental data (mean ± SME) obtained at a storage temperature of $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the dashed line represents the model result.

Fig. 10 shows model validation by comparing the experimental and predicted value of the mean equivalent diameter of the ice crystal over 21 days of storage at $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The model shows a good agreement with the experimental data, as indicated by the low Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 1.51%. This demonstrates high accuracy of the model in predicting recrystallization behavior of a partially frozen beef. The slight discrepancies between the experimental and modelled data could be caused by experimental variations and microstructural homogeneity in the meat matrix itself which the Ostwald ripening model did not fully capture. Additionally, the model does not account for the initial ice crystal size distribution, which may partly explain the minor discrepancies observed (Iggland and Mazzotti, 2012).

To assess the relationship between recrystallization rate and kinetic degradation rate, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted. The quality degradation rates used for correlation were obtained from Mwakosya et al. (2025), as part of the same experimental campaign in which microstructural characterization of the present study was performed. Both analyses were carried out on beef samples derived from the same raw material and stored under identical conditions ($-1.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). In that study, the quality parameters of beef, such as drip loss, texture, color difference, Tbars, and Tvb-n were monitored over 21 days of storage. Table 2 summarizes the correlation coefficients (r) and corresponding p -values. It can be seen that the recrystallization rate was significantly negatively correlated with texture ($r = -0.95$, $p = 0.02$). Conversely, recrystallization rate was significantly positively correlated with drip loss ($r = 0.91$, $p = 0.04$), Tbars ($r = 0.92$, $p = 0.04$), Tvb-n ($r = 0.928$, $p = 0.036$), and color difference (ΔE) ($r = 0.92$, $p = 0.04$).

These results imply that higher recrystallization rates were associated with reduced texture quality, increased drip loss, greater lipid oxidation and protein degradation, and undesirable color. Mechanistically, recrystallization promotes the transformation of small ice crystals into larger ice crystal bands, leading to severe cellular disruption of

muscle tissue (Wang et al., 2020). The formation of large extracellular ice crystals ruptures cell membranes and reduces the structural integrity of muscle fibers, which in turn explains both the observed texture loss (reduced firmness) and the elevated drip loss upon thawing due to reduced water-holding capacity (Xia et al., 2012; Tao et al., 2023). Cellular disruption also exposes lipids to oxygen and releases oxidative enzymes such as lipoxygenase, oxidase, and pro-oxidants from damaged organelles, which further enhance lipid oxidation (Boonsumrej et al., 2007; Tan et al., 2021; Tao et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2024). Lipid oxidation not only produces rancid flavors but also promotes oxidation of myoglobin and other pigments, resulting in color deterioration (Leygonie et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2021; Yifei et al., 2021). Similarly, cellular disruption leads to the release of proteolytic enzymes, which enhance proteolysis and the accumulation of volatile basic nitrogen compounds thus explaining the increase in Tvb-n values (Du et al., 2022). Although storage at lower temperatures ($-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) reduced the overall extent of oxidation and proteolysis compared with higher superchilling temperatures, degradation still progressed during prolonged storage. This underlines that even under these conditions, recrystallization-driven microstructural damage remains a key driver of quality deterioration.

From a sensory perspective, textural loss, drip loss, oxidation, and color changes are well recognized as major contributors to consumer-perceived meat quality (Teng et al., 2023). Taken together, these findings demonstrate that recrystallization is not only statistically correlated but also mechanistically linked to multiple quality degradation pathways in partially frozen beef. This highlights the importance of selecting appropriate storage temperatures that would minimize recrystallization and preserve beef quality during superchilled storage.

4. Conclusion

Microstructural assessment of beef samples stored at $-1.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-2.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ revealed that storage temperature had significant impacts on the muscle integrity. For instance, the ice volume fraction increased from 35–45% on day 1 to 55–70% on day 21, with the highest value observed at $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Similarly, the ice crystal size increased from 36 μm to approximately 70 μm on day 21 with significant reduction of ice crystal number. Samples stored at $-1.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-2.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ showed relatively minor changes in ice crystal volume fraction and ice crystal size throughout the 21-day storage, unlike those stored at $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ which exhibited a notable microstructural changes. These findings suggest that, storage at $-1.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-2.8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ represents a thermodynamically and kinetically stable superchilling range, effectively limiting recrystallization and preserving muscle microstructure compared with lower storage temperatures. In addition, X-ray μCT proved to be a non-destructive, effective, and promising tool for quantifying 3D microstructural changes at the macroscopic level for partially frozen beef during storage.

Most importantly, a recrystallization model was developed using experimental mean ice crystal size data, and the recrystallization rates were found to increase with decreasing storage temperature. Moreover, correlation results showed that, the recrystallization rate was highly correlated with the quality degradation rate. These results highlight the importance of maintaining the defined superchilling temperature range consistently throughout the cold chain to effectively limit recrystallization and preserve beef quality during extended storage.

To the best of our knowledge, the recrystallization model presented

Table 2
Comparison of recrystallization rate and quality degradation kinetic rate.

Recrystallization rate	Quality degradation kinetic rate					
		Texture	Drip loss	Tbars	Tvb-n	Color difference (ΔE)
Pearson correlation		-0.95	0.91	0.92	0.93	0.92
p -value		0.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04

in this work is a novel approach for describing the recrystallization phenomenon in partially frozen food products during superchilled storage. The model developed provides a basis for predicting ice crystal growth in partially frozen food products. This, in turn, will help to optimize the partial freezing processes and distribution chains, ensuring product stability. However, there is a need to explore different packaging solutions in order to minimize temperature fluctuations during the storage of partially frozen beef. Moreover, future research should focus on developing more comprehensive models, such as the population balance equation coupled with energy balance, to fully capture the ice crystal size distribution and energy balance dynamics during recrystallization. This will give insights into ice recrystallization in partially frozen beef during storage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anjelina W Mwakosya: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Graciela Alvarez:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Fatou Toutie Ndoye:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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